

The Press Release as Communication Technology: A Media Ecology of a Key Public

Relations Tool

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Preprint. Version: v1.0, Friday, April 25, 2025.

Presented at the 32nd Annual Einhellig Interdisciplinary Forum (EIDF), 2025

Missouri State University, Springfield, MO

Abstract

The historical emergence of press releases has become an integral part of public relations research as Public Relations strategies are being tremendously influenced by modern communication technologies. The paper aims to study press releases as communication technology under the purview of media ecology theory. Public relations practitioners mainly consider press releases as communication tools, glorifying companies, and organizations' familiarity with the public and target groups. This paper critically identifies and defines their structural traits and biases which have an ecological role in society as well as the political sphere too. This ubiquitous and multipurpose role of press releases as public relations tools often disseminate information from various organizations while creating social and political campaigns to reach target groups. Despite this fact, organizations choose press releases as a mode of communication to accomplish and glorify the company, subsequently, biased, and sensationalizing information through press releases generates mistrust and favoritism in the organization and makes them questionable to the media and public.

Keywords: Press Release, Media Ecology, Public Relations

The Press Release as Communication Technology: A Media Ecology of a Key Public Relations Tool

The history of the press release as communication technology and its attendant social impact is of considerable importance to the field of media and communication. The ubiquity and multipurpose use of the press release as a public relations tool, along with its ongoing appeal as a means to convey messages from organizations, corporations, and campaigns to target groups, ensure its centrality as a communication strategy in the digital age. Over the past few decades, our communication technologies and environment have changed substantially, but the press release has remained a valuable and popular public relations tool.

Scott (2009) observes that modern technologies have contributed to various social changes that create problems for public relations practitioners. Despite these challenges, email and other digital communication platforms make it easier to reach journalists and, by extension, the public through press releases. So, even as modern technologies have ushered in key changes in society, press releases continue to be a vital means of reaching the public through the news media. Emphasizing the most significant uses of the press release and its subsequent evolution in modern communication, Autzen (2014) noted that:

What is most thought-provoking about this historic public relations event is that The New York Times newspaper actually printed the press release word-for-word. And that is what often happens today with press releases from scientific institutions. Like copy-pasted texts they get printed word-for-word in newspapers and on internet media platforms of any kind with ‘pressing the copy-paste buttons’ being the only contribution from the journalists working in the media. (p. 2)

In explaining how press releases get published and reach the public – often without any changes or other editorial interventions, Autzen highlights the perceived credibility that news media outlets assign to press releases. It is worth noting that the development of press releases and their centrality to public relations campaigns and efforts generally, as well as to the arena of politics specifically, represents one of the most important communication innovations of the modern era.

Prompted by the direct, if multidimensional, implications of technology on prevailing modes of discourse and communication, this paper aims to study press releases as a technology of communication central to the theory and practice of public relations. To achieve this objective, this paper unfolds in three parts. In the first part, I examine the historical development of the press release as communication technology, paying particular attention to how it was created and popularized over time. In the second part, I review the existing research regarding the press release, identifying its defining structural traits and subsequent biases. Finally, in part three, I explore the social implications of the press release on society, while assessing and commenting upon its unique role in modern political campaigns specifically.

Historical Development of the Press Release as a Communication Technology

Press releases are concise statements issued by companies, institutions, or campaigns to announce some newsworthy action, event, initiative, or invention; typically, a press release is sent to journalistic outlets in the hopes that they will recirculate it or report on it (Catenaccio, 2008). The uses of press releases vary from situation to situation, depending on the category of events and issues and considering the target audience. According to McLaren & Gurau (2005), different organizations use press releases to shape their company's image, showing how they are persuading their target groups to prove to them how much the organization is worthwhile

reassuring others that they are still good. Usually, press releases contain multifaceted softer information that includes the likeliness of technology and products, while language, format, and structure could be convened by the press release issuer (Gong, 2023). Thus, the press release plays a crucial role in publicizing information that has a significant impact on people or groups of people.

Nowadays, this history of press releases is often discussed in the research arena, especially in public relations. It is mentioned that the modern and classical version of press releases was first introduced by the earliest American public relations practitioner Ivy Ledbetter Lee. The study found that the first press release was created by the founder of public relations, Ivy Lee in 1906, after an accident at Pennsylvania Railroad, aiming to provide authentic news to the journalists, while inviting the reporters and photographers too to take scene (Ward-Johnson & Guiniven, 2008). Later, the initiative of Lee was greatly praised by the newspapers and concerned officials for the openness and safety he created for the passengers. The statement of this press portrays Lee's declaration of principles disseminated to the newspaper's owners in 1905, addressing the intended way of circulating information to newspaper agencies (Fisher et al., 2021). Since then, it has always been seen Press Release as a much-needed part of the public relations practitioner, and most importantly for those who are interested in PR education and research (Aronson & Ames, 1993).

Over the years, the press release has become a quicker and more reliable tool of communication, disseminating information to others with the rise of the telegraph, telephone, and later internet. According to Nye (1997), the early stages of networked communication of telegraph and telephone provide a vital background for understanding computer network communication. All the communication technologies (e.g. mail, telegraph, telephone, and

internet) show a steady pattern, determining the quality, prices, and uses although the internet was predominantly developed with monthly rates depending on the size of the links and its uses sometimes interrupt easy access to people (Odlyzko, 2001). The replacement and utilization of each communication technology renders some significant changes and opportunities that make it more easily accessible and acceptable to others. According to Crawford (2009), the first telegraph was replaced by a telephone which helped internet access when high-speed internet entrance was replaced by dial-up. Thus, the way of telecommunication service was developed and evolved from a basic structure to a legal structure.

With the advent of press releases and their wide acceptance the development of communication technologies is essential. In response to the evolution of media releases or media news, the term 'press' is generally referred to as a media release to the audiences, while a press release is being considered the primary communication tool of public relations as media outlets are increasingly dependent on it to feature news and stories (Gandy, 1982). According to Boumans (2018), recently, the ongoing influence of press releases on news media created a development platform in the media outlets, while newspapers grappling with several challenges in today's media world, minimizing media persons, moving to online news portals, dwindling readership and decreasing the advertising income (Lewis et al., 2008 & Manning, 2000).

Therefore, with the advancement of modern communication technologies, the form of press release and its role in creating widespread media relations have somehow changed considerably but its main purpose has remained determined. Tkalac Verčič (2016) states that the evolutions of technology and social media have overwhelmingly been changed by their form and purpose, but still today press releases represent desirable tactics that are paradoxically used as successful tools for media relations. In the age of digital communication technology, the most

important thing for distributing a press release is timing. The timing of issuing a press release and circulating it among the audiences can create a more immediate and impactful response. According to Vorvoreanu, (2008), the overall range of press releases has evolved, modifying it into a news communication technology too more often used by public relations practitioners and marketing professionals as well.

Amid the development of communication technologies, the changing trend of a press release from conventional published by print media to digital media published by online platforms (Suciati et al., 2021). Nowadays, people usually depend on online media to get information in the earliest possible way, resulting in declining the appeal of traditional media. According to 2018 research by the Pew Research Center (2018), one out of every three Americans prefer to read news online, considering it the second most favored media after television. This study proves that it is not like the consumers reading the news online only but everyone which presents press releases as a communication tool of credibility and branding. According to Arief and Saputra (2019), during the era of industrialization, the evolution of the roles and functions of PR has changed greatly, while passing the third PR 3.0 in which various types of social media platforms have been using and taking the place of traditional media platforms, creating trust in public minds. In the era of digital communication technology, both social media and press releases have been effective communication tools used by organizations to disseminate information (Astutik et al., 2018), where press releases are a great source of information in the form of news issues and send to the media outlets (Ardianto, 2011).

Social media has a great impact on press releases as organizations use these platforms easily to reach more people. Scott (2007) opined that the “new” form of press releases focuses more on information and shifting direct delivery from senders to receivers across various media

and target audiences via the internet, measuring the impact these releases on attitudes, opinions, and behaviors, aligning with the nature of research. However, this new form of press release offers a dynamic way of communicating tools to reach audiences within a few seconds and has immediate results that work as the Social Media Release (SMR). According to Steyn et al., (2010), the SMR has been explored as a proper combination of the conventional press release and digital social media, evolving as a response creating interconnectivity facilitated by social media, comparing it with also digital press releases which enhance additional elements desired by the reporter and journalists before they create their content and transmit them to broadcasting. Thus, the way press releases have been evolving with digital technology and are expected to enter the PR 4.0 era where Artificial Intelligence (AI) and big data era are present.

Arief & Saputra (2019) also opined that public relations practitioners use various tools to disseminate press releases to different media, targeting the organization's campaign while managing digital content, audio-visual, and data analytics by applying AI technologies. Although AI is still in the early stages of its development, it has already started influencing the PR industry, generating and preparing press releases that make PR practitioners reliable and confident in getting media attention (Lonna cited in Mardhika, 2023).

In the field of PR, AI has control over framing content like press releases and managing the crisis. It also helps to speed up the work of PR practitioners and helps them to be more engaged in creative work.

In an organizational setting, it is more important to consider when AI is being used for solutions, creating press releases by AI assistance rather than humans that clarify the role of AI as the outcome of expectations and needs (Rahikainen, 2020). Thus, press releases have been adopted in modern communication technology in media and public relations.

The Structural Traits/Biases of the Press Release

Press Releases as a Communication Tool

A press release is a written statement which is commonly referred to as a media release, prescribed by organizations, targeting the members of news media and people to announce something claimed as news value (Pitt et al., 2011). Generally, it is sent, posted, faxed, and emailed and even considered social media platforms by communication practitioners, public relations personnel, and communication to various media outlets (e.g. newspapers, radio stations, and television channels). Press releases have been successfully used as a form of communication since the concept was developed. Over the hundreds of years of initiation, it is still considered the best way of advertising, exhibiting, and announcing products to the target audience. The study found that press releases are deliberately predetermined, as to why it unveiled a set of metapragmatic features that make the journalists and people understand them and even follow copy-paste policy for media reporting (Sleurs & Jaobs, 2005).

The press release is one of the basic and powerful communication tools used by various companies, academic institutions, and organizations to disseminate information to media outlets and the public. When a crisis happens in any organization, usually public relations practitioners first consider press releases to overcome any unwanted situation. According to (Choi & park, 2011), the primary objective of the issuance of a press release is to inform the public through media organizations to mitigate a crisis when it arises. Besides, press releases have a greater impact and positive value than any form of communication tool in public relations. The significance is denoted when the press releases are written on the letterhead of the company as media outlets treat them as valued and urgent. This is how a press release is considered a fundamental tool of public relations communication to announce the news, build public relations,

obtain media coverage, inviting to visit websites, optimize the organization's search engines, inform target groups, and overcome crisis communication.

The use of press releases by news media is very usual considering its media acceptance and attention. According to Maat (2007), PR practitioners furnish press releases dynamically and distinctly, aiming to disseminate information to the journalist to reach a broader audience while also shaping the journalistic narratives. To enhance communication, organizations provide press releases, and press release archives, where the organization's publications, initiatives, success, and recent and future activities are reflected which are indispensable and essential for brand promotion, reputation, and media communication (Kirat, 2007). Thus, press releases serve as a communication tool for various organizations to obtain media coverage.

The use of press releases as a form of communication massively influences the readers when the link to the organization's website is mentioned on the letterhead of press releases. It interests people to drive the website traffic to get more information that potentially leads to reaching the organization's virtual exposure on a broader scale. Campbell et al., (2019) opine that online promotional campaigns often consider various materials including press releases, sharing them with partner organizations by using social media (e.g. Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram) as this approach significantly helps to reach audiences and encourages readers to visit the website. Besides, the online distribution of press releases can increase the visibility of an organization's website through Search Engine Optimization (SEO). According to Vorvoreanu (2008), the supreme goal of online press releases is to enhance an organization's visibility and reliability to the audience, crafting and introducing online content and optimizing search engines. Moreover, press releases have a great role in meeting crisis communication anytime usually happens in the organization. The study found that press releases play an official role for an

organization during a crisis, analyzing the content issued by stakeholders that unconnected the organizations going through the crisis (Coombs et al., 2019). Thus, the information in press releases provides messages and clarification to the people minimizing communication strategy during a crisis.

Chief Structural Properties of Press Releases

To understand the elements of press releases and the selective information disclosure that shape public perception and media narratives while the press releases have both structural properties and subsequent biases. Structural properties often discuss the attention-getter sentence, and the main content of the paragraphs, like quotes, and supporting evidence. Over time, the reliance on press release materials has been intensified with the advent of digitalization, as it forces news agencies to cut their reporting staff off. Jackson & Moloney (2016) opined that when the media houses wrestle to provide enough news with limited sources, then press releases have been experiencing huge successes placing stories as an elective to editorial subsidies. Despite the significant structure properties of press releases, it has subsequent biases that misleading information to the people.

Most press releases follow the same structure and format, starting with an announcement first followed by elaborated information while including details for further communication (McLaren & Gurău, 2005). Generally, the structural properties of the press releases include a headline, date of issuance, leading contents, body, quotes, and contact information, where most of these parts have their distinctive ways of presenting and disseminating information. Every element of the structural properties of a press release effectively disseminates news and information to the media and people. The first thing is the headline of a press release that commonly takes the attention of the readers, concisely summarizing the main points.

According to Guillamon-Saorin, E., Osma, B. G., & Jones, M. J. (2012), headlines are generally presented as a framing tool that grabs and holds attention, aiming to shape readers' thoughts, ideas and emotions, furthering to influence their point of view. Maleková (2013) opines that the headlines of press releases echo the newspaper headlines considering the structural features of the designation of it. So, writing a killer headline has a great role in press releases. Along with the headline, the next most important bit of a press release is top line or lead. According to Murray (2015), the first line of the press release expresses the overview of the story which does not exceed 115-20 words, answering the "Five Ws" (who, what, where, why, and when) to make a great appeal of it. Press releases are usually written and prepared by almost journalistic standards so they can disseminate information. Janecek (2006) wrote a book on *What Makes an Effective Press Release: An Orientation Approach of Public Relations Practitioners and News Editors in Sport* that says that;

Regarding the essential elements of a press release, several public relations texts do exist and all appear to fall into generally four categories: news value, format, style, and 10 content. Often listed elements under news value include: having a well-defined purpose, focusing on one central subject, being newsworthy, factual, appropriate quotes, and pertinent information. Elements commonly listed regarding format include things such as spacing, paper, identification, release date, margins, length, paragraphs, slug lines, headlines, proofreading, and timing. Elements commonly listed under style include appropriate gender use, capitalization, abbreviations, numbers, spelling, and punctuation p. 9-10).

Structurally, a press release should focus on the news value, format, style, and 10 contents to whom every element has its distinctions and sub-elements. If media personnel see the press

releases have news value, they instantly consider making it published without further hesitation while both format and style help them to get a better understanding of it. Furthermore, the 10 contents of a press release usually discuss the pyramid structure and answer five Ws questions and objectivity.

Biases of Press Releases

Along with the structural properties, press releases have subsequent biases, addressing sensationalized headlines, emotive language, and reinforcing quotes to garner news coverage and reach more people. Press releases, sometimes, address a discovery in a way to attract or grab attention, aiming to support a particular agenda (Alexandar et al., 2022). To set the agenda, information is disseminated in a distorted and sensationalized way through media which often confusion and redundancies in the audience's minds. According to Sumner et al., (2014), press releases often claim bold and exaggerated statements without proper information and authenticity. This exaggeration potentially misleads readers and audiences by presenting information in a biased way. However, exaggeration differs from institution to institution, depending on the situation and the nature of the events and activities. In the context of university press releases, they mostly used amplified words and languages in comparison to journal press releases, assuming that the press officials are under pressure to fabricate the tone to generate anticipation and excitement (Sumner et al., 2016).

The development of press releases and their evolution in academia, industry, and news media has a great significance in influencing readers, and audiences. Most importantly, the uses of press releases no longer exist in communication and news media but also science and research. Press releases bridge the gap between academia and news media by establishing a dominant link, harnessing an effective communication of scientific research as people

deliberately reply to the information and messages conveyed by press releases (Yu et al., 2020). So, the strategy of using press releases to disseminate information about any kind of organization has become a great deal of research.

Sometimes, the bias of a press release usually comes in various forms like its language and tone, selective sources, quote and spin, agenda setting, and conflict of interests. Generally, organizations target vending their products and other salient issues as part of the agenda-setting process (McQuail, 2005). Sometimes, press releases are written to consider the agenda while this strategy influences the tone, contents, and even the language, leading further to the biases of the issue. To set up the agenda, organizations are considering offering incentives to the media to obtain media attention. The study found that the ratio of incentives in press releases is 1.282 which indicates the value being increased by a factor to the media (Schafraad, P., van Zoonen, W., & Verhoeven, P. (2016). Although press releases serve as an important communication tool to disseminate information, it is much more essential to evaluate them critically to avert potential bias too.

The Impact of Press Release on Society and the Role of Public Relations on the Political Sphere: A Media Ecological Perspective

To explore the impact of press releases on society and the role of public relations in the political sphere, this paper will analyze the Media Ecology Theory (McLuhan, 1964). Discussing the importance of the medium, the Canadian philosopher McLuhan pointed out that “All media work us over completely. They [media] are so pervasive in the personal, political, economic, aesthetic, psychological, moral, ethical, and social consequences that they leave no part of us untouched, unaffected, unaltered. The medium is the message” (McLuhan, 1964, p. 26). Communication technology affects us in two ways; first, it influences our efficiency and

productivity and justifies overexposure to new technologies while the new technologies lead people to connect with others to do different things that cause changes in society and its roles in the societies too (Al-Saqqa et al., 214). Hence, press release as a tool of communication technology certainly has a huge impact on society too.

Similarly, public relations in the context of communication technology have a great role in the political area. The public sphere has been considered as a place between society and state (Habermas, 1996), which often leads to maintaining democracy. Public relations play a fundamental role in the process of communication frameworks that are considered supportive of making a robust democracy and its practices (Sommerfeldt, 2013).

Impact of Press Releases on Society

From the media ecological perspective, press releases play a significant role in society, addressing how communications shape media and societal dynamics. The societal dynamics often being influenced by various media press releases as they serve primary source of disseminating information, shaping societal discourse and discussion, media and power dynamics, and affecting public opinion to build credibility and trust in the society while also shaping the media literacy of a society. In society, it is often seen that various groups arise while interest groups always try to put pressure on other groups by disseminating information that favors them to be influenced by any means while press releases have always been part of this process. According to Andsager (2000), most viewpoints of interest groups derive from press releases and are attributed to them in news coverages.

The interaction of press releases with society happens in various ways, depending on nature along with its prospective appliance on society. Sometimes, a society's decision-making process is influenced by press releases as they frame media agendas and impact public

perceptions and decisions. The study found that the agenda-building process and ratio for media outlets and press releases is 0.096 (SD = 0.087), while 10 percent of newspapers' stories are influenced by the organization's press releases (Boumans, 2018). It indicates that press releases issued by any organization always have a great impact on changing people's perceptions and beliefs. Press releases have a direct influence on society as they get published on various media platforms and organizations' websites without editing and modification.

Williams (1994) discussed many reasons why press releases have great power to persuade editors and the decision-making process of a society at large. He states that "over time, releases can help define an organization's character and core values," (p. 7). Over the decades, press releases have been performing the role of a tool for reshaping the organization's character and values that must have been affecting society while the organization plays a broader role in it. Most importantly, press releases have a greater role in working and making images and reputation for the organization. According to Huston (2014), various organizations disclose their goodwill and reputation by considering press releases as tools, disseminating their success and effectiveness. According to Lassen (2006);

In recent times, a remarkable development has witnessed that the press releases are going to be published on various websites directly by the respective organizations, and companies issued by the officials. With the rise of the internet and digital media platforms, various organizations have gained tremendous popularity and freedom as they can issue press releases anytime and upload them on their respective websites accordingly so that they do not need to rely on journalists and media.

Discussing the impact of press releases on society from the media ecological perspective, it has been opined that press releases underscored the interconnectivity among media systems,

organizational communication, and societal dynamics that help to constitute and construct meaning in shaping public dialogue.

Role of Press Releases on Public Relations

The role of press releases is crucial in public relations within the media ecological perspective. The term media ecology as a field of studying communication technology has a significant influence in that it creates and presents an overall overview of how press releases work within the broader scale of the media landscape. Logan (2007) defines media ecology as not only the study of media but also the study in the realm of language, culture, and technology and their interactions with each other, demonstrating these four domains that work like living organisms, evolving and acting with the organizations like a media ecosystem. From the perspective of media ecology, press releases play the role of media in the study of public relations, disseminating information to media, providing journalists with precise content; developing relationships between PR professionals and media; creating media content in shaping the digital media platform; influencing media while working like a media ecosystem.

According to Gilpin (2008), over the years, public relations experts have been considering press releases and news releases to communicate with audiences through various media, while press releases serve as autobiographical narratives through various organizations to convey and manage their identity. Press releases address factual representations while tailoring unique voices and tones for the organizations. Ertürk (2015) considers press releases, in terms of public relations, as an important communication tool that aims to help convey newsworthy information about the organization to public and media outlets. Public relations officials consider sending press releases to different media outlets and even sometimes publish them on their respective websites too, aiming to reach more people and target audiences. This strategy of using

press releases in public relations has an effective and long-term effect, addressing the organization's crisis, introducing new products, ensuring media outreach, establishing credibility building trust with stakeholders, and maintaining open communication with media. Young, P. (2013) terms that public relations practitioners try to influence mass media not only for reach but also to create long-term relationships as they always wish to them engaged, considering the over popularity and the rise of digital media still an effective mode of communication reaching more audiences with a very limited time. So, press releases have been one of the best communication tools for public relations over the decades. Morris and Goldsworthy (2008: 105) put it strongly:

The PR industry's reluctance to admit to the centrality of media relations . . . flies in the face of the understanding of PR in wider society. To most outsiders, PR is forever, and overwhelmingly, associated with journalism and the media, with press releases and press conferences.

So, the role of press releases is multi-dimensional in public relations while it also continues to be working on building relationships between journalists and public relations practitioners. This relationship, however, determines regularly sending valuable, authentic information to the journalists by public relations practitioners that creates, furthermore, credibility and trust and helps to build a media ecosystem. For instance, journalists rely on the contents and materials sent by public relations professionals which also corresponds to their connection. Their research (Burton, 2007; Davies, 2008; Moloney, 2006) opines that journalists are gradually relying on the information and contents provided by public relations partitioners without necessarily justifying and supplementing the resources with additional information and inquiry. Thus, journalists are often dependent on the materials shared by public relations professionals which makes a better understanding and building good ties with each other.

According to Sissons (2012), 50 to 80% of news content shows the influence of public relations professionals, determining the clear impact of them comes from press releases mostly.

Press releases play a multifaceted role in disseminating information in public relations within the context of media ecological perspective. It also works as a conduit for information, content, materials, and the most powerful tool of communication in public relations to define the organization's activities and make successful promotions.

Role of Press Releases in the Political Sphere

Press releases have a great political role along with their subsequent impacts on society and public relations. Media ecology discusses the study of the media environment in which people's perceptions, beliefs, and understanding are increasingly influenced, while press releases serve as a medium of the media environment. Media ecology is the study of media *as* media, which follows from McLuhan's (1964) famous maxim, "The medium is the message" (p. 7). The role of press releases is very similar to medium with media ecological perspectives in the field of the political sphere.

According to DeGregorio (2009), political parties follow advocacy policies implementing two strategies; "information" and "mobilization.". DeGregorio also mentioned that both these strategies are addressed by issuing press releases when people show reluctance to mobilize and when any issue is raised press releases focus on the decorating information, while circulating press releases helps to make a frame within the groups of people. Political parties often use media to publish their agenda before the people through press releases. They usually disseminate messages to the public by writing press releases on their party's letterhead to get the media's attention too. Lenaerts, G. (2002) opines that press releases can easily reach the target groups

through various media when it seems successful in disseminating the information to the intended audience.

Press releases also play in shaping the agenda of political discourse by conveying specific events, issues messages, and narratives in shaping the agenda of political discourse by conveying specific events, issues, messages, and narratives. Political parties consider press releases to produce their party-affiliated agenda (Hopmann et al., 2012), while both parties and political institutions depend on press releases too much to carry out the party's manifestations (Garud-Patkar & Kalyango, 2017).

According to Lacatus (2019), during the 2016 American Presidential Election, the campaign of Hillary Clinton used press releases as a communication tool for highlighting the different aspects of the party's policy and agenda with its continuation of successful policies and agenda implemented by Obama administration, while securing minimal use of press releases put Trump limited to the access to public of it various campaign policies and positions to make a successful election.

Senninger & Wagner (2015) press releases empower political parties to rapidly respond to the actual event, helping them to analyze the campaign policies and even assist parties to mobilize people during the national election. It also manifests political issues by addressing and aligning with the parity's goals and ideologies. From a media ecological perspective, press releases make interaction among media, technologies, and various institutions that help to shape the political communication of parties. Political communicators consider sending press releases to the media houses as it has a great chance of making them into the news and this informational communication leads to a greater functioning of democracy (Donsbach & Brad, 2011). Thus,

press releases have significance in various activities of political parties and institutions to obtain a democratic government.

The political behavior of people is greatly influenced by press releases as the agenda of political parties is massively circulated through various forms of media and even in the digital age it takes a second only to reach target groups easily. According to Rogowski & Stone (2020), any formal statement or press release issued by political parties may have a great possibility of getting subsequent media response and coverage, while circulating the content and material by using social media and email that have a competitive advantage on contemporary political issues. In the digital age, press releases can easily be interacted with around social media, various websites, and for further information that allows to keep contacting with political parties, and media practitioners, while enabling them to engage in political dialogue and discussion. According to Burford (2012), press releases are aggregated with the predominant data conveying political standpoint with conventional information, while 74% of the press releases are considered in the isolation opinion category, suggesting that most of the press releases represent political association via oral communication.

Thus, press releases prolifically serve the media ecology to analyze how politicians' political parties, political institutions, and various pressure groups deal with the media aiming to address the needs of the people, while political parties consider press releases as their narrative of circulating agenda and propaganda.

Discussion and Conclusion

In conclusion, it has been observed that since the development of press releases, it has been used widely considering its language, framework, and structure could be convened by the organization. It has also been playing a significant role in communication technology over the

years as a quicker and more reliable communication tool. As the time approached quickly, press releases have developed in a sophisticated manner and evolved greatly with modern communication technology, modifying it as a media communication tool often being used by public relations practitioners and professionals of any organization.

Over the years, the reliance on press releases has been increased by various organizations. The materials and structural properties of press releases have been intensified even with the advent of digital technology. The structure of a press release often helps an organization to effectively disseminate news and information to the media and people broadly while having significant structural properties of press releases, it has also some subsequent biases that provide misleading information to the people. In a brief statement, the overexposure of press releases through various media, and the organization's website creates biases of information, setting mispropaganda and agenda to a particular issue. When journalists of different media outlets publish press releases without further editing and proofreading, there is a great chance of implanting this bias among the public too. And even in the digital age, the possibility of sensationalizing information through press releases on social media has a great ramification. All these biases and favoritisms of press releases not only mislead people's perceptions but also create skepticism on different media and social media.

However, press releases also generate an immense amount of impact on public relations practitioners and practices. The history of press releases and their successful evolution in technology make these communication technology tools a widespread appearance in society and the political sphere that reflects public opinion and participation on the pavements of the decision-making process and democratic government.

Before concluding, I would like to make it clear and applicable that despite having some biases, after the invention of the telegram, telegraph, and printing press, press releases are a great invention in shaping public opinion, and beliefs within a society, have more appliance in modern communication technology, and have significant role public relations and political sphere too.

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